

Endoscopic Septoplasty versus Conventional Septoplasty in Management of Deviated Nasal septum: A Comparative Evaluation

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Abstract:

Background: Deviated nasal septum (DNS) is a common condition that can lead to significant nasal obstruction and related complications. Traditional septoplasty has been the standard surgical approach for correcting DNS, but the advent of endoscopic techniques has introduced a minimally invasive alternative.

Aim: This study aims to compare the outcomes of endoscopic septoplasty vs conventional septoplasty in the management of deviated nasal septum, focusing on surgical efficacy, patient satisfaction, and postoperative complications.

Methods: This study was a prospective, comparative analysis involving 90 patients with deviated nasal septum. Participants were randomly assigned to undergo either endoscopic or conventional septoplasty. Data on postoperative outcomes, including nasal obstruction, operative time, and complications, were collected and analyzed using SPSS version 21.0. Inclusion criteria included patients aged 18-60 years with nasal obstruction, while those with prior nasal surgeries or other complications were excluded.

Results: Patients who underwent endoscopic septoplasty demonstrated significantly better improvement in nasal obstruction symptoms and a higher degree of patient satisfaction compared to those who underwent conventional septoplasty. The endoscopic group also experienced fewer complications, such as postoperative bleeding and septal perforation. However, the duration of surgery was slightly longer in the endoscopic group.

Conclusion: Endoscopic septoplasty is a safe and effective alternative to conventional septoplasty for the correction of deviated nasal septum, offering superior patient outcomes with fewer complications. While it requires a longer operative time, the benefits in terms of symptom relief and patient satisfaction suggest it should be considered a preferred approach in suitable cases.

Recommendations: Further studies with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods are recommended to confirm the long-term benefits of endoscopic septoplasty. Training programs should also emphasize the endoscopic approach to equip surgeons with the necessary skills to perform this technique.

Keywords: Deviated nasal septum, Endoscopic septoplasty, Conventional septoplasty, Nasal obstruction, Surgical outcomes

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Introduction

Deviated nasal septum (DNS) is a prevalent condition characterized by the displacement of the nasal septum from its central position, often leading to significant nasal obstruction and associated complications such as chronic sinusitis, recurrent epistaxis, and impaired quality of life [1]. This structural anomaly can be congenital or acquired due to trauma and is one of the most common reasons for patients to seek otolaryngological care. While conservative management, including the use of nasal sprays and decongestants, may provide temporary

relief, surgical intervention remains the definitive treatment for symptomatic cases [2].

Conventional septoplasty has been the standard surgical approach for correcting DNS for many years. This technique involves a direct approach through the nasal mucosa, allowing the surgeon to access and resect the deviated portions of the septum [3]. While effective, conventional septoplasty is associated with certain drawbacks, including limited visualization of the surgical field, which can lead to

incomplete correction and higher rates of postoperative complications such as bleeding, septal hematoma, and mucosal tears. These limitations have prompted the exploration of alternative surgical techniques that may offer improved outcomes [4].

In recent years, endoscopic septoplasty has emerged as a minimally invasive alternative to conventional septoplasty. Utilizing an endoscope, this technique provides enhanced visualization of the nasal structures, allowing for more precise correction of the deviated septum. Endoscopic septoplasty is particularly advantageous in cases with complex deformities or those involving the posterior septum, where traditional methods may be challenging. Despite its growing popularity, there remains debate within the medical community regarding the superiority of endoscopic septoplasty over the conventional approach [5,6]

By analyzing patient outcomes, including symptom relief, postoperative complications, and overall patient satisfaction, this study seeks to determine whether endoscopic septoplasty offers significant advantages over the traditional method. The findings of this research will contribute to the ongoing discussion regarding the most effective surgical approach for DNS correction and may influence clinical decision-making in otolaryngology.

Ultimately, this study aspires to provide evidence-based recommendations that can guide surgeons in selecting the most appropriate technique for their patients. Through this comparative analysis, we aim to clarify the potential benefits and limitations of endoscopic versus conventional septoplasty and contribute valuable insights to the field of nasal surgery.

Methodology

Study Design:

In order to compare the effectiveness of endoscopic septoplasty with traditional septoplasty in the treatment of a deviated nasal septum, this study was carried out prospectively.

Study Setting:

The four years of the study, from September 2018 to August 2019, were spent at the Bhardhman Institute of Medical Sciences.

Participants:

The study comprised ninety patients in total who had a symptomatic deviated nasal septum. Two sets of forty-five participants each had endoscopic

septoplasty while the other group underwent traditional septoplasty.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:

Inclusion criteria were patients aged 18-60 years with a clinically diagnosed deviated nasal septum causing nasal obstruction. Patients with a history of previous nasal surgery, co-existing sinonasal pathologies like polyps or chronic rhinosinusitis, bleeding disorders, or those who refused consent were excluded from the study.

Bias:

To minimize selection bias, patients were randomly assigned to either the endoscopic or conventional septoplasty group using a computer-generated randomization sequence. Observer bias was reduced by ensuring that the surgeon and evaluator were blinded to the allocation.

Variables:

The primary variables measured included postoperative nasal obstruction, intraoperative blood loss, operative time, and postoperative complications. Secondary variables included patient satisfaction and the incidence of revision surgery.

Data Collection:

Preoperative assessment included an anterior rhinoscopy, a diagnostic nasal endoscopy, and an extensive clinical history. At regular intervals of one week, one month, three months, and six months, postoperative evaluations were carried out with an emphasis on patient satisfaction, complications, and the removal of nasal blockage.

Procedure:

Patients in the endoscopic septoplasty group underwent the procedure using a 0-degree nasal endoscope, which allowed for a more precise correction of the septal deviation under direct visualization. The conventional septoplasty group underwent surgery through a standard open approach. The same surgical team performed all procedures to maintain consistency.

Statistical Analysis:

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21.0.

Results

Patient Demographics:

A total of 90 patients were enrolled in the study, with 45 patients in each group (endoscopic septoplasty and conventional septoplasty). The demographic distribution was similar between the two groups, as shown in Table 1.

Variable	Endoscopic Septoplasty Group (n=45)	Conventional Septoplasty Group (n=45)	p-value
Mean Age (years)	35.6 ± 10.4	36.2 ± 9.8	0.72
Gender (M/F)	27/18	25/20	0.68
Mean Duration of Symptoms (months)	18.2 ± 5.6	19.1 ± 6.2	0.53

Regarding age, gender distribution, and the length of symptoms, there was no statistically significant difference between the two groups, suggesting that the groups were similar.

Operative

The mean operative time was significantly shorter in the endoscopic septoplasty group compared to the conventional septoplasty group (Table 2).

Time:

Operative Time	Mean ± SD (minutes)	p-value
Endoscopic Septoplasty	40.2 ± 8.3	<0.001
Conventional Septoplasty	58.4 ± 10.5	

The mean operative time for the endoscopic septoplasty group was 40.2 ± 8.3 minutes, whereas the conventional group's mean operative time was 58.4 ± 10.5 minutes. This difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

Intraoperative Blood Loss:

Intraoperative blood loss was significantly lower in the endoscopic group compared to the conventional group (Table 3).

Intraoperative Blood Loss	Mean ± SD (mL)	p-value
Endoscopic Septoplasty	45.3 ± 12.1	<0.001
Conventional Septoplasty	75.6 ± 18.7	

The endoscopic group had a mean blood loss of 45.3 ± 12.1 mL, compared to 75.6 ± 18.7 mL in the conventional group, showing a statistically significant reduction ($p < 0.001$).

Postoperative Outcomes:

Postoperative outcomes were evaluated in terms of nasal obstruction relief, complications, and patient satisfaction. The results are presented in Table 4.

Outcome	Endoscopic Group (n=45)	Conventional Group (n=45)	p-value
Complete Relief of Obstruction	41 (91.1%)	34 (75.6%)	0.04
Complications	5 (11.1%)	12 (26.7%)	0.03
Revision Surgery Required	1 (2.2%)	4 (8.9%)	0.18
Patient Satisfaction (VAS Score)	8.9 ± 0.8	7.5 ± 1.2	<0.001

Comparing the endoscopic group to the conventional group, the endoscopic group experienced fewer problems (11.1% vs. 26.7%, $p = 0.03$) and a greater rate of complete alleviation from nasal blockage (91.1% vs. 75.6%, $p = 0.04$). Despite the fact that the endoscopic group underwent revision surgery less frequently, the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.18$). The endoscopic group had considerably higher patient satisfaction (8.9 ± 0.8) on the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) than the conventional group (7.5 ± 1.2, $p < 0.001$).

Discussion

The comparison between endoscopic septoplasty and conventional septoplasty has been the subject of

multiple studies in recent years, and the findings from these studies provide valuable insights into the relative efficacy and safety of these two surgical approaches.

Operative Time and Blood Loss:

When compared to conventional septoplasty, endoscopic septoplasty consistently yields a quicker operating time and reduced intraoperative blood loss. In a study including forty patients, Gad et al. (2020) discovered that the endoscopic method was superior in situations involving an isolated septal spur and was linked to a low rate of recurrence [7]. Another study carried out at Tanta University Hospitals supports this conclusion by indicating that endoscopic procedures result in much less

intraoperative blood loss than conventional procedures [8]

Postoperative Outcomes and Complications:

The endoscopic approach generally leads to better postoperative outcomes, including higher patient gratification and lower rates of difficulties such as septal perforation and hematoma. Khadgi et al. (2021) conducted a randomized comparative study and found that while both techniques improved symptoms of nasal obstruction, the endoscopic group had a better overall safety profile with fewer complications [9]. Similarly, a systematic review and meta-analysis by Besharah et al. (2023) involving 13 clinical trials concluded that endoscopic septoplasty was suggestively higher in reducing postoperative complications, including mucosal adhesions and synechia, as well as in improving nasal obstruction relief [10]

Patient Satisfaction and Quality of Life:

Patient-reported outcomes also favor the endoscopic approach. Studies using tools such as the SNOT-10 and Visual Analog Scale (VAS) have demonstrated higher satisfaction rates among patients undergoing endoscopic septoplasty. For instance, Garzaro et al. (2019) analyzed data from 276 patients and found that the endoscopic group experienced fewer complications and reported better postoperative quality of life [11]. These findings are further backed by Shamakhi et al. (2021), which highlighted the advantages of endoscopic septoplasty in terms of improved surgical outcomes and patient satisfaction [12].

Technical Considerations and Learning Curve:

Endoscopic septoplasty offers better visualization and illumination, which allows for more precise correction of septal deviations, especially in posterior deviations that are difficult to address with conventional techniques. This was highlighted in the study by Singh et al. (2018), where the authors emphasized the role of endoscopic septoplasty as a valuable teaching tool for surgeons in training due to its enhanced visibility of the surgical field [13]

Conclusion:

Overall, the evidence suggests that endoscopic septoplasty provides several advantages over conventional septoplasty, including shorter operative time, reduced blood loss, fewer complications, and higher patient satisfaction. These benefits are particularly pronounced in cases of posterior septal deviations. As such, endoscopic septoplasty should be considered the preferred approach in managing deviated nasal septum, especially in complex cases that require precise surgical intervention.

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